

Mosque-Based Islamic Character Education for Millennials

Ma'zumi^{1*}, Syihabudin², Nanah Sujannah³, Najmudin⁴, Jakaria⁵, Suja'i⁶
^{1,2,3,4,5,6} Universitas Sultan Ageng Tirtayasa, Indonesia

*Corresponding Author : Ma'zumi, Syihabudin, Nanah Sujannah, Najmudin, Jakaria, Suja'i

ABSTRACT

The phenomenon of moral degradation in the millennial generation requires immediate and strategic handling. At this time it needs to be followed up by maximising the function of the mosque which is not only a place of worship but also a means of education for today's millennial generation. This article aims to analyze the role of the mosque itself in character development in the millennial generation. The research method uses a type of approach in the form of a literature study on the role of mosques in developing the Islamic character of the millennial generation. The problem in this study is How is mosque-based millennial generation Islamic character education? The result is that the character education of the millennial generation can be carried out by the mosque, by revitalizing the role and function of the mosque through coaching programs and holding innovative, interesting, and systematic activities that can strengthen the character of the millennial

Keywords: Islamic Character Education, Millennial, Mosque

INTRODUCTION

Character building is not a process of memorization or imitation without understanding. Character building requires a process that involves cognitive aspects, affective aspects, and psychomotor aspects. The character-building process is called character education by the author. Character education requires habituation (habituation), such as habituation to do good, speaking honestly, politeness, being ashamed to cheat, not being lazy, and even keeping the environment clean (Bulkani et al., 2025). Character is not formed immediately but needs to be trained seriously and balanced to achieve the ideal shape and strength. Individual character development can take place within the social and cultural environment concerned. This means that development can be carried out in an educational process that is still related to the socio-cultural environment of the community and nation (Bornstein & Güngör, 2009).

The socio-cultural development of societies and nations, even more broadly human civilization is influenced by the rapid development of technology and continues to grow. Technology is both a challenge and an opportunity for human life. The development of technology, which is now entering the 5.0 era, has given birth to the gadget generation, this term is used to mark the emergence of the millennial generation in the current era. (Makarović & Rončević, 2020) The gadget generation in their lives is always faced with devices that contain elements of information technology. All of these devices become an inseparable part of their lives. It is as if various kinds of high-tech tools have become the most important part of life.

The millennial generation must be based on religious and social values, so that they use and utilize technology for what is useful, becoming a medium in developing the quality of their potential. Not according to their lusts, which results in the birth of various problems in life, such as an economy with predatory capitalism, politics that justifies all means, drug trafficking, human trafficking, promiscuity, LGBT practices, environmental destruction, and so on, environmental destruction and so on.

The millennial generation in reality shows two conditions, first: Moral degradation as a result of the weakening of religious and social values owned by the community which leads to the formation of new cultural clashes due to the adverse effects of technological developments; and second: In the era of the industrial revolution 4.0, the role of the mosque has not been able to attract the interest of the millennial generation. The mosque is only used as a place of worship, not as a cozy place, a positive hangout place, a place for discussion, a place for empowering youth competence, regeneration, and other activities (Darmawan & Marlin, 2021).

The mosque, besides being a place of worship for Muslims, is the most strategic medium for the development of the people, moral, spiritual, educational, economic, social, and cultural aspects. Mosques are institutions, such as madrasas, that have a very important role in *tafaqquh fi al-din* (deepening religious knowledge) and science. The mosque is the center of the development of Islamic civilization. In historical records, the first thing the Prophet Muhammad SAW built in Medina when he emigrated from Makkah was the Mosque (Quba mosque), about three miles from the Prophet's Mosque. The construction of the mosque, based on its function and role is part of the manifestation of faith. The mosque was a place of ritual worship as well as a means of proselytizing Muslims in building the civilization of the people.

Throughout the course of Islamic history, the contribution of mosques in building the civilization of the people is very strategic and significant. Thus, for the mosque to play a role in building a generation of people capable of building a good civilization, the mosque needs good management, and professional human resources according to the developed *takmir* field, including digitalization in this millennial era. So that the mosque is optimally able to respond to the reality of the people. The mosque prepares a generation that can respond to the development of information and communication technology in its positive use.

Building the character of the millennial generation through the mosque is not limited to congregational prayer, but must be done with mosque *takmir* programs related to education, such as TPA (Qur'anic Learning Center for Children), TPQ (Qur'anic Learning

Center) , *Majelis Taklim* (Islamic learning assembly), discussion groups, etc., even entrepreneurship programs for economic independence of the people, as a form of mosque providing welfare to the people. Character building through the mosque can be done with moral knowing, moral loving, and moral learning strategies. It is hoped that the formation of habits of thought (students have the knowledge, willingness, and skills to do good) and a comprehensive understanding will produce mosque congregants (millennial generation) who have a strong character, have resilience in science, faith, and righteous behavior, both personally and socially. (Ma'zumi, Saleh, and Maisaroh 2023)

The mosque takmir is oriented towards three forms of understanding (Ma'zumi, 2019):

- 1) The mosque as a religious institution, namely the mosque functions to connect people's awareness at a spiritual level with the public sector, such as economics, politics, education, and culture. Mosques need scholars;
- 2) The mosque is a manifestation of piety and good deeds, namely the mosque as a means of practice *ubudiyah* and practice *muamalah*. The mosque becomes the star point of activity; and
- 3) The mosque is a manifestation of culture, namely the mosque is a means of building a culture that is of interest to various levels and layers.

Various efforts have been made to overcome moral degradation. One of the efforts is mosque-based Islamic character education for the millennial generation. So the step that must be taken is to optimize the role of the mosque through various mosque *takmir* programs so that the mosque becomes an institution that accommodates the activities of the millennial generation by utilizing information and communication technology that is directed, appropriate, and targeted. It is hoped that the millennial generation will have the self-awareness to be able to love, be diligent in the mosque, and become obedient and obedient servants to Allah SWT. Based on these two phenomena, the writing of this article aims to analyze how mosque-based millennial generation Islamic character education.

The research was conducted for two fundamental reasons, namely first: The crisis that hit students (as well as political elites) indicates that religious and moral education obtained from school (college) has little impact on changes in Indonesian human behavior. Even now what appears is that in general human behavior is incoherent between speech and action (Ma'zumi, et.al 2023); second: None of the previous studies examined mosque-based millennial generation Islamic Character Education, most of the previous studies only focused on examining the role of mosques on the millennial generation, not specifically discussing character education.

METHOD

This study employs a library research approach, which involves examining various books, academic articles, and relevant prior studies to obtain a theoretical foundation for the problem under investigation (Sarwono, 2006). The focus of this research is to analyze the role of the mosque in developing Islamic character among the millennial generation. To enhance methodological rigor, this study applies a systematic procedure in collecting and selecting literature, drawing from credible academic sources such as peer-reviewed journal articles, books, and conference proceedings accessed through databases including Google Scholar and Scopus (Bakhmat et al., 2022). The selection of sources was guided by specific criteria: relevance to mosque-based education, Islamic character education, and millennial studies; publication within the last ten years; and clear academic credibility.

The research process includes collecting library data, reading and recording relevant information, processing research materials, and describing and interpreting findings. These steps are further strengthened through a structured analytical approach using thematic analysis, which involves data reduction, categorization, comparison of concepts, and interpretation to identify key patterns and relationships across the literature (Katsiroumpa & Galanis, 2026). A total of 20 relevant sources were analyzed in this study, consisting of core and supporting literature related to mosque-based education, Islamic character education, and millennial studies. Through this approach, the research not only presents a descriptive overview but also provides a critical synthesis and conceptual understanding of mosque-based Islamic character education in the context of contemporary millennial society.

FINDING AND DISCUSSION

Finding

Islamic Character Education

The practice of Islamic teachings has a prototype that is exemplified for mankind. The form of practicing Islamic teachings in a kaffah (whole), namely Muhammad SAW, has the characteristics of Shidiq, Tabligh, Amanah, Fatonah. These traits reveal the character of qur'any (M. Q. Ali et al., 2020).

Character is inherent in every individual. Character, which develops gradually through natural and nurturing factors, is a personal identity, which shapes a person's views, attitudes, and behavior (Mujahid, 2021). In Islam, character is a pure and positive human

nature. However, in the process, fitrah is influenced by various factors, namely internal factors and external factors. Some are following the vision of its Creator, and some are against it.

There are two different opinions regarding character and morals. First, the character is said to be synonymous with morals (Yuliharti, 2019), because both are behaviors, traits, habits, and morals based on Islamic values sourced from the Qur'an and Hadith of the Prophet Muhammad. This Islamic character is essentially akhlaq al-karimah (noble character). Noble character is a trait, character, and behavior that shows a good relationship with Allah (Khaliq) and fellow creatures based on Islamic values; Second, character is not identical to morals. Character is more about individual characteristics. Character encompasses the whole personality, which is the tendency of the soul to behave spontaneously.

According to Syukur & Munawaroh (2021) in (Ma'zumi et al., 2023) Islamic character education is the process of character building based on Islamic religious teachings. Based on various values, namely religious, social, and legal values, according to Asmani (2012) in Halawati (2020) cited by (Ma'zumi et al., 2023) character values are classified into five main values, namely character values about Allah SWT.; self; others; environment and nationality.

Creating a generation that has an Islamic character is based on building the relationship of each individual, namely the relationship with God, relating to oneself, relating to others, and relating to the environment (Basuki & Febriansyah, 2020). (1) Character values related to self-relationship with God, among others: faith and piety, namely being Allah SWT as God (fulfilling His commands and not doing what He forbids); (2) Character values related to self, among others: responsibility, hard work, discipline, healthy living, honesty; (3) Character values related to others, including respect for differences, respect for the work of others, help in kindness, social ethics; and (4) Character values related to the environment, including social and environmental care (appropriate and targeted utilization of natural resources).

Islamic character consists of good attitudes, habits, and character traits, which are learned, understood, and applied in daily life based on Islamic religious teachings by the Qur'an and Assunnah, and are always trained to do good (Fitriani 2018). Or Islamic character is thinking, understanding, paying attention, saying, acting, and practicing ethical values under Islamic teachings (Dewi, 2020). Building this Islamic character involves three domains, namely cognitive, feeling, and action. Cognitive involves reason as the main prerequisite for achieving faith and piety. Cognitive builds and underlies feelings that will

appear in actions that have experienced habituation, not acting outside of reason and rationality (Alika Atha Amani, Saniyah Rizky Amalia, 2006).

According to Amilda et al. (2023), Islamic character values are honest, tolerant, disciplined, hardworking, creative, independent, democratic, curious, peace-loving, social and environmental care, responsible, and love for the country. These values are internalized in a planned and systematic manner, both monolithically and integrated. The effort to internalize Islamic character values strategically and systematically is called Islamic character education. Or by Taufik called moral education (Taufik, 2020).

Millennial Generation

The first generation of the Industrial Revolution took place in 1765. The Industrial Revolution in England began with the invention of the steam engine by Denis Papin (1647-1712), Thomas Newcomen (1663-1729), and James Watt (1736- 1819) (Zaim, 2020). Steam-driven machines help or even replace human and animal labor. Machine-powered technological works with steam power developed rapidly, such as trains, cars, and printing machines.

The second generation of the industrial revolution was the application of the concept of mass production with the utilization of electric power. The inventors were Michael Farady, Thomas F. Edison, and Nicolai Tesla. The use of electricity began in January 1882 in England, and then in New York in 1885. Technological works such as electric-powered engines were developed, replacing steam-powered engines. This extended to broadcasting and communication devices, such as radio, telephone, telegraph, and AC and DC electricity.

The third generation of the Industrial Revolution began in 1970, when the invention of PLC (Programmable Logic Control), an electronic circuit that can control machines, using only a program. The fourth generation of the industrial revolution began in 2000, with the existence of large data transactions, Smart Factory (Zaim, 2020).

Millennials are those born between 1981 and 2000 (H. dan L. P. Ali, 2017). The millennial generation is also known as Generation Y. This term began to be recognized and used in a major US newspaper editorial in August 1993 (Statistik, 2018) The results of a study conducted by the Boston Consulting Group (BCG) with the University of Berkley in 2011 in the United States about the USA millennial generation are as follows:

- 1) Interest in conventional reading is declining.
- 2) Must have a social media account as a communication tool and information center.
- 3) Prefer cell phones over television.

4) Family is their center of consideration and decision-making

Education responded to the industrial revolution with its technological advances as both a challenge and an opportunity. As a challenge, technological advances as a means of communication and a source of information that is unlimited by distance and time, will be fatal if the tendency is negative utilization. As an opportunity, education has the opportunity to conceptualize a digital-based pedagogical theoretical foundation and make creative and inclusive innovations related to learning strategies, media, and models. It is hoped that the positive response to education can build a better socio-cultural society.

The characteristics of millennial generation cultural values include making technology a lifestyle, multitalented, multilanguage, more expressive and explorative, optimistic, confident, instantaneous, working and learning more interactively through teamwork, collaboration and group thinking, independent and structured in the use of technology, communication gadgets, in internet access prefer visual images (Osika, 2018).

Human relations with space and time, the characteristics of the millennial generation in communicating are instant communication in a real-time environment, and network development, namely developing networks that allow this generation to connect and collaborate. Related to the basic principles of human relations with nature, it has the principle of utilization and preservation of the natural environment.

The millennial generation is divided into several groups, namely:

- 1) The Students Millennials group is a generation that is still of school age or is still preoccupied with the obligation to study. Smartphones have entered this group, social media has also begun to be used by school teenagers.
- 2) Working Millennials Group, which are millennials in the working stage (productive age)
- 3) Family Millennials group, namely millennials who have started a family or are starting to think in that direction (Yoris Sebastian, Dilla Amran, 2016)

The millennial era is characterized by the speed of information, technological sophistication, transportation, and communication strengthened by strong organizational and management arrangements. The millennial generation or Generation Y is a generation that develops with various innovations in information technology (Netters and Nexters). This generation is more flexible towards new things with all its possibilities. This generation is often illustrated as a generation that is cozy with change. Hence the tendency to educate the millennial generation. Educating millennials who tend to do new things, and are confident is done with a participatory, loose, and open approach

Mosque

A mosque, as we all know, is a special building used to perform *fard* prayers (especially) for Muslims. More specifically, what is meant by the mosque here is the place where the congregational prayer is established, whether the Friday prayer is established in it or not. Historically, the mosque was the first institution built by the Prophet Muhammad in the Medina period. The first mosque founded by the Prophet on 12 Rabiul Awwal of the first year of *Hijriyah* (July 28, 622 AD) was the Quba Mosque located in the city of Medina. The Quba Mosque at the beginning of its establishment was intended to guide the *muttaqin* and *mutathahirin* congregation and a control center for building civilization. That's why Allah SWT gave positive appreciation for its establishment.

According to Abd al-Rahman Ibrahim Fauzan (2003) in (Ma'zumi, 2022) during the caliphate, the mosque was no longer the center of control, but the mosque remained the center of worship, Islamic preaching, and community development (building human resources), the center of study and development of various scientific disciplines so that the mosque has educational facilities such as *kuttabs*, libraries, and dormitories. This *Kuttâb* is where the madrasa was founded, which later developed into a university.

The mosque is one of the important elements in the structure of Islamic society. The mosque has great meaning in life, both physical and spiritual. Apart from functioning as a place of worship, the mosque also functions to foster and educate people to become people of faith and piety. The mosque has a very strategic role in improving the quality of society (Wibowo et al., 2023). Mosques face challenges and demands that continue to roll in intellectual circles and society. Globalization and advances in information technology cannot be ignored, and the dominance of information media in society will have many consequences, including opportunities and threats (Hidayat et al., 2023).

Maximizing the *takmir* masjid automatically revives the function of the mosque. It is hoped that the role of the mosque as a center for Islamic studies, a center for social-religious transformation, a center for economic development, and a center for coaching, training, and empowering human resources, not just a place to perform worship rituals, like most mosques in the village. Thus, the mosque should have a good management system and involve reliable human resources in the field of *takmir* (Hakim, L. et al. 2022), and a serious, professional, and proportional mosque management is needed.

To prosper the mosque means being a mosque worshipper and managing its functions and roles. This can only be done by people who have a transactional commitment to their belief in Allah as the owner of the mosque; people who believe in the last day who have material and spiritual responsibilities; people who pray, who congregate in building the religiosity of the people; people who do zakat, who have an attitude of caring for others, generosity and empathy; and people who fear Allah (people who are knowledgeable again believers who manifest it for the welfare of themselves and others solely because they get Allah's appreciation) (Ma'zumi, 2022).

The mosque as the center of community development refers to the principle of Islamic teachings on the integration of *mahdhah* worship with social worship, so that the mosque must emit light that shines on the environment and its congregation. The worshipers must be able to bring the substance of the teachings (Islam) out of the mosque walls and into the community area. Therefore, every activity carried out in the mosque must provide benefits to the community. This includes solving any problems that arise in society.

Prospering the mosque can be done with a series of activities carried out jointly by several people, including (Ma'zumi, 2019):

- 1) *Idarah* (managerial and administrative activities) The mosque cannot be managed individually. The mosque becomes a necessity to be managed collectively, and requires careful planning, strategic programs, and is carried out by professional people. So that the management of the mosque can run well, a mosque *takmir* is formed, commonly referred to as DKM;
- 2) *'Imarah* (activities that lead to the guidance of the congregation). Empowering the mosque with a variety of activities, which include services to worshipers, Islamic learning assembly activities, *madrasa diniyah*, Qur'an education parks, a commemoration of Islamic holidays, cooperatives, medical centers, empowerment of *amil zakat* institutions, and others. Specifically *'imarah* can include education, economy, social, health, *da'wah*, politics, and others. These programs are within the duties and responsibilities of the section/division/field that is responsible to the chairman.
- 3) *Ri'ayah* (activities related to physical development - facilities and infrastructure). A field that includes mosque construction, rehabilitation, and maintenance of the mosque. Thus the mosque that has been built can maintain splendor, beauty, purity, and cleanliness. So that everyone will feel safe, comfortable, and peaceful when in the mosque.

Millennials are close to technology The management and programs of the mosque's *takmir* involve and are connected to the digital world and are a special attraction for the millennial generation. The mosque is expected to be a magnet and attraction for the millennial generation to prosper the mosque. Among these roles are: Mosque Prosperity Council (MPC) must be digitally literate, create interesting content, organize the mosque more comfortably, develop information management systems, and other millennial and digital-based public services. The role of the mosque can reach the development of social community activities that can improve the economy increase the intellectual intelligence of the congregation, and be able to provide solutions to problems faced by the congregation

Mosque *Takmir* Managerial

Mosque management is managed by people who are professionals in their fields, involving the millennial generation. It is hoped that their direct involvement in the management of the mosque *takmir* will build an Islamic character born as a generation of mosques.

Three elements in the Islamic teaching system, namely *aqidah*, worship, and *muamalah*. *Aqidah* is the basis for fulfilling *shar'i* obligations in the form of worship (building the quality of self-relationship with God) and *muamalah* (building the quality of relationships with fellow creatures). Good *muamalah* is a manifestation of the quality of worship, as a form of practicing the values of worship. Therefore, worship is the basis of the mental building of the people in building other aspects such as economics, politics, government, and others.

The influence of the mosque as a place of religious, social, knowledge, economic, and political development is based on the construction of the mosque as social development. This is because the mosque is not only a noble place, but also a place that has an important role in fostering obedience, worship, *muamalah*, and community development. As written by Ma'zumi (Ma'zumi, 2022), the role of the mosque can develop aspects: (1) religious aspects: Formation of Islamic society; Media *ta'aruf* and brotherhood; (2) aspects of knowledge development: Mosque Prosperity Council, youth study groups, education, etc.; and (3) the mosque as a medium for economic development: mosque cooperatives, mosque-based entrepreneurs, etc.

In general, the mosque has three main functions, namely (1) theological function, namely the mosque as a place of liberation from polytheism; (2) worship function, the mosque as a place to perform actions that show obedience and devotion to Allah SWT.; (3) social function, namely the mosque as a safe, comfortable, peaceful place, plays an active role in the welfare of the congregation (people); and (4) educational function, namely the mosque as an educational institution that prepares the best generation of people formally and non-formally. Overall, the mosque functions as a gathering place for discussion, deliberation, *dauroh*, and seminars, gaining knowledge, sharing experiences, becoming a center for da'wah and social activities, fostering the ummah, becoming a center of Islamic culture, and awakening the ummah. To realize these functions, the mosque needs adequate facilities and infrastructure, including resources for professional managers (mosque administrators), good management and organization, and active participation of mosque congregants (residents around the mosque in particular and Muslims in general) (Hakim, 2022).

Micro, the role of the mosque in the life of Muslims is as a place of ritual worship. Macroly, the mosque is the center of da'wah and Islamic culture, the center of regeneration of the ummah, and the center of the awakening of the *ummah*. The optimal role of the mosque lies in the programs of the mosque *takmir* which are full of values, to build *khaira ummah*. This synergizes with whole human development as a generation of the nation.

The reality of mosques that have not maximized the interest of the millennial generation, and the reality of the millennial generation with flexible, creative, and innovative characteristics, requires an integrative and comprehensive response. It cannot be a priori and cannot be postponed so that the role of the mosque towards the millennial generation is optimal, it must involve the millennial generation itself, starting from the management of the mosque, *Idarah* (matters relating to administration), *Imarah* (matters relating to the mosque *takmir program*), and *ri'ayah* (matters relating to mosque buildings, mosque facilities, and infrastructure, maintenance, cleanliness, and mosque security).

Discussion

Mosque-based Islamic Character Education for Millennial Generation

The first generation of the Industrial Revolution took place in 1765. The Industrial Revolution in England began with the invention of the steam engine by Denis Papin (1647-1712), Thomas Newcomen (1663-1729), and James Watt (1736- 1819) (Zaim, 2020). Steam-driven machines help or even replace human and animal labor. Machine-powered technological works with steam power developed rapidly, such as trains, cars, and printing machines. However, from an analytical perspective, the discussion of industrial development should be understood not merely as historical background but as a contextual factor influencing changes in educational needs and youth behavior in contemporary society.

The second generation of the industrial revolution was the application of the concept of mass production with the utilization of electric power. The inventors were Michael Farady, Thomas F. Edison, and Nicolai Tesla. The use of electricity began in January 1882 in England, and then in New York in 1885. Technological works such as electric-powered engines were developed, replacing steam-powered engines. This extended to broadcasting and communication devices, such as radio, telephone, telegraph, and AC and DC electricity.

The third generation of the Industrial Revolution began in 1970, when the invention of PLC (Programmable Logic Control), an electronic circuit that can control machines, using only a program. The fourth generation of the industrial revolution began in 2000, with the existence of large data transactions, Smart Factory (Zaim, 2020).

Millennials are those born between 1981 and 2000 (H. dan L. P. Ali, 2017). The millennial generation is also known as Generation Y. This term began to be recognized and used in a major US newspaper editorial in August 1993 (Statistik, 2018). Millennials are strongly influenced by digital environments, which shape their communication patterns, learning preferences, and social interactions, thereby requiring adaptive and context-based educational approaches (Jayanth & Ganesh, 2025; Ozuem et al., 2021). The results of a study conducted by the Boston Consulting Group (BCG) with the University of Berkley in 2011 in the United States about the USA millennial generation are as follows:

- 1) Interest in conventional reading is declining.
- 2) Must have a social media account as a communication tool and information center.
- 3) Prefer cell phones over television.
- 4) Family is their center of consideration and decision-making

Education responded to the industrial revolution with its technological advances as both a challenge and an opportunity. As a challenge, technological advances as a means of communication and a source of information that is unlimited by distance and time, will be fatal if the tendency is negative utilization. As an opportunity, education has the opportunity to conceptualize a digital-based pedagogical theoretical foundation and make creative and inclusive innovations related to learning strategies, media, and models. It is hoped that the positive response to education can build a better socio-cultural society.

The characteristics of millennial generation cultural values include making technology a lifestyle, multitalented, multilanguage, more expressive and explorative, optimistic, confident, instantaneous, working and learning more interactively through teamwork, collaboration and group thinking, independent and structured in the use of technology, communication gadgets, in internet access prefer visual images (Osika, 2018). These characteristics imply that character education for millennials must be designed using participatory and experiential approaches rather than purely normative instruction.

Human relations with space and time, the characteristics of the millennial generation in communicating are instant communication in a real-time environment, and network development, namely developing networks that allow this generation to connect and collaborate. Related to the basic principles of human relations with nature, it has the principle of utilization and preservation of the natural environment.

The millennial generation is divided into several groups, namely:

- 1) The Students Millennials group is a generation that is still of school age or is still preoccupied with the obligation to study. Smartphones have entered this group, social media has also begun to be used by school teenagers.
- 2) Working Millennials Group, which are millennials in the working stage (productive age)
- 3) Family Millennials group, namely millennials who have started a family or are starting to think in that direction (Yoris Sebastian, Dilla Amran, 2016)

The millennial era is characterized by the speed of information, technological sophistication, transportation, and communication strengthened by strong organizational and management arrangements. The millennial generation or Generation Y is a generation that develops with various innovations in information technology (Netters and Nexters). This generation is more flexible towards new things with all its possibilities. This generation is often illustrated as a generation that is cozy with change. Hence the tendency to educate the millennial generation. Educating millennials who tend to do new things, and are confident is done with a participatory, loose, and open approach.

Preparing a generation becomes effective by involving and preparing according to the consumption of the generation it is building, in this case, the millennial generation. Therefore, mosque-based education should not only function as a religious space but also as an adaptive learning environment that integrates spiritual values with contemporary youth culture. It has been described that the millennial generation is a generation that is sticky with digital. Social media is their communication and information tool. A generation that is expressive, interactive, explorative, and collaborative. A generation that is connected without distance and time through network development. This is done by all millennial generation groups, both those of school age and productive age.

Mosque-based millennial generation Islamic Character Education is carried out with four approaches, first: knowledge, namely character values are directly programmed in special activities; second: Integrated, namely character values are integrated into the management and activity programs of the mosque *takmir*, namely by involving the millennial generation both in mosque management, program preparation, and implementation of activity programs; and third: Habituation, namely the practice of character values in daily activities; and fourth: Exemplary, namely providing exemplary examples with righteous behavior.

From a conceptual standpoint, these four approaches represent an integrative framework that connects cognitive, affective, and behavioral dimensions of character education. The managerial scope of the mosque includes *idarrah*, *'imarah*, and *ri'ayah*. Effective implementation of these dimensions requires professional management and the active involvement of millennials in organizational processes, which has been shown to increase engagement and ownership.

1) Idarah (matters related to managerial and administrative matters)

Mosques that have strategic, planned, and measurable programs cannot be managed individually. Mosques require collective management. The mandate for the management of the mosque is given to the mosque *takmir* management which is generally known as the Mosque Prosperity Council (MPC) which consists of the Chairman, Secretary, Treasurer, sections/divisions/fields in charge of mosque *takmir* programs, such as da'wah, education, economy, and others, with the principle of competing in goodness and service to the community (Ma'zumi, 2019).

(a) Mosque Management

Mosque management by MPC is required to master technology. MPC is not anti-technology. For example, several contemporary mosques have implemented digital platforms such as social media-based da'wah, online study sessions, and youth-oriented content, which significantly increase participation among younger generations. In the 4.0 era, where information and communication are based on digitalization, it is an opportunity for mosques to expand the reach of da'wah so that the mosque is not only for the congregation, the community around the mosque. Thus, the mosque is required to be network-based, so that the audience can take advantage of the *takmir* program from anywhere and anytime. In mosque management like this, the millennial generation can be positioned as a networking skill and representation of their generation's ideas in *idarrah*, *imarah*, and *ri'ayah*.

To carry out its duties and functions, MPC needs a mutually agreed direction, the result of deliberations involving the millennial generation. This direction is commonly referred to as the DKM's Articles of Association and Bylaws. A *takmir* program plan is also made, along with an estimation of implementation, which includes targets, time and place, budget, and performers. All activities in the *takmir* program are not only for consumption by the congregation around the mosque; they are also publicized for the syiar of Islam, encouraging people to participate, and expanding the purpose of *da'wah*. All of this is done by the millennial generation.

(b). Mosque Secretariat

The secretariat is the driver's carriage. All mosque management activities start from the mosque secretariat, including planning programs, meetings, and other tasks. This place can also be referred to as the representative office of the board. The secretary is responsible for cleanliness, order, security and beauty. The secretariat, in particular, serves as the mosque's public relations. (Hakim, 2022).

(c) Mosque financial management

Article 6 of the Regulation of the Minister of Religion of the Republic of Indonesia Number 6 of 2006, the purpose of the Mosque Prosperity Board is to improve the welfare of the mosque, both in terms of management, maintenance, and prosperity. Mosque financial management is one of the determining factors for the prosperity of the mosque which provides benefits to the people. The mosque is allegedly able to become a driver of the people's economy.

According to Sochimim (2016) as cited Pradesyah et al. (2021), the mosque is a nonprofit and non-profit organization, namely an organization that is not oriented towards making a profit. This is because the source of mosque funds comes from zakat, infaq, shadaqah, waqf, as well as other community and government donations. These funds must be managed with a good and productive financial management system, accountable and transparent. Mosque funds are divided into productive and consumptive forms. Mosque funds in consumptive form are given to mosques to meet the physical needs of the mosque. While the mosque's productive funds are managed by providing capital loans to the community to open businesses around the mosque.

A mosque's financial management system helps in managing the organization's finances. Monitoring incoming and outgoing funds can be done with the assistance of financial management. Reporting on the use of funds for activities is well-documented for each event. Similarly, procedures for depositing and withdrawing funds are also regulated to ensure smooth operations and accountability. The mosque's administrative system should have tidy records, accountability, and transparency in regular monthly, quarterly, or semi-annual reports (Pradesyah et al., 2021).

Mosque financial management policies that are productive, accountable, and transparent, according to Muhib (2018) as cited by Pradesyah et al. (2021), are first: Receipt: evidence of receipt from the source of funds is recorded according to its qualifications, such as shadaqah, infaq, zakat, waqf and so on. The reporting of these funds is recorded regularly and informed to the congregation of the mosque; second: Every expenditure made by the mosque is recorded by including clear evidence to fulfill the elements of accountability and transparency; third: budgeting and control refers to the

funds allocated to carry out the activity plan included in the mosque program and to provide tools to monitor and supervise these activities; fourth: financial reports in the form of expenses and receipts with accompanying documents and information; fifth: mosque financial management is based on POAC (Planning, Organizing, Actuating, Controlling).

2) 'Imarah (matters relating to the mosque *takmir* program, fostering worshipers)

The mosque is a social development, not just physical and material development. The mosque is not only a noble place but also an important place to develop obedience, worship, science, and *muamalah*. Therefore, prospering the mosque in an organized manner can only be done by people who are trustworthy, honest, professional, and proportional (Ma'zumi, 2022).

Takmir is the administrator of the mosque (Big Indonesian Dictionary). According to Abdul Aziz Masyuhuri (Masyuhuri, 2018), "*amaratul masjid*" or "*takmir masjid*" is an effort, activity, and action to enliven the mosque with religious activities that can bring someone to the pleasure and grace of Allah SWT.

The mosque *takmir* program is arranged and planned creatively and as interesting as possible, relevant to the times, and includes spiritual, intellectual, social, economic, political, and cultural aspects, so that it is attractive to the millennial generation.

Millennial Generation Development, including:

(1) Mosque Youth

Activity programs for mosque teenagers are compiled and planned by involving the millennial generation according to their interests and divisions. Activity programs should be packaged as interesting as possible and become the consumption of the millennial generation, such as leadership training programs; Islamic studies; lectures; arts and culture; calligraphy; and so on. Trainers, resource persons, and assistants for these activities whose delivery of material is not rigid, open, and very easy to digest, have many followers on social media such as YouTube, Instagram, or others. Thus, it is hoped that the millennial generation will visit the mosque and be directly involved in the prosperity of the mosque.

Each of these activity programs can bring up character values that will be internalized, such as honest, responsible, and confident characters in leadership training programs; faith and piety characters in Islamic studies programs, and lectures; characters respect for work and diversity, and love of beauty in arts and culture programs; and calligraphy.

(2) Education

According to the author, education is an effort to develop and build the quality of self-confidence, so that it can carry out its duties and responsibilities as a human being in a perfect manner, both about itself, to God, to others, and its life environment. The mosque as an institution and place of non-formal education has a mission to improve the quality of the congregation prepare a generation of faith, piety, knowledge, pious deeds, and morals, and become good and responsible

citizens. The future of Islam, the nation, and the state rests on the shoulders of the younger generation.

Education as one of the *takmir* programs, can directly carry out the process of internalizing character values through a special character education program. Character education is a system of naming character values that include components of knowledge, perception, and action in realizing it, both towards God Almighty, self, others, the environment, and the state. Character building is a process carried out from an early age.

Education that can be developed in mosques for early childhood is the Al-Qur'an Education Park. For the millennial generation in the form of *tahsin Al-Qur'an*, Al-Qur'an competency training such as recitation of the Al-Qur'an, *syarhil Qur'an*, scientific work, calligraphy, and others and so on.

(3) Entrepreneurial training

Humans are born with the potential to do righteous activities according to their abilities and work according to their competence. All human activities fall within the scope of economic activity. The idea of economic empowerment is not only studied in formal educational institutions and universities, but mosques as non-formal educational institutions since the beginning of the history of Islamic civilization have become the center of economic control of the people.

Revitalizing the role and contribution of the mosque in building the economy of the people is needed to respond to and accommodate the needs and problems of the people. The mosque moves to become a pioneer, preparing a place to introduce home industry products, even conducting independent mosque-based businesses, such as shops, hotels, cooperatives, and so on. The mosque-based entrepreneurial vision is the mosque's contribution to prospering the people. The mosque is no longer a beggar in raising funds for managerial and *takmir* mosque financing.

In the entrepreneurial training program, Islamic characters can be internalized for the millennial generation, such as optimistic, hardworking, and independent characters from craft and craft training programs, entrepreneurship, mosque-based economic development training such as cooperatives, and so on.

(4) ZISWAF Management Training

The character values internalized to the millennial generation through ZISWAF management training are honest, trustworthy, empathetic, hardworking, and responsible characters. ZISWAF management training can be carried out through activities such as insight briefing and ZISWAF management.

(5) Halal slaughter training

Consuming halal and *thayyibah* is also a commandment of shara'i law. Shar'i animal slaughter (halal) is not as simple as the practice, which is to cut the neck, esophagus, throat, and two arteries using a sharp instrument or in other ways justified by Islamic law in the name of Allah SWT. Shar'i animal slaughter is included in the realm of Islamic law

to provide certainty of the halalness of slaughtered animal meat, so the guarantee of halalness starts from the production of slaughtered animals, distribution of slaughtered animals, halal slaughter, distribution of slaughtered animal meat until it reaches the hands of consumers for consumption, as well as its hygiene.

Regulation of the Minister of Health of the Republic of Indonesia No. 1096/2011 concerning Hygiene, Sanitation and Food Safety, in its application there are six principles, namely (1) Selection of food ingredients, (2) Storage of food ingredients, (3) Food processing, (4) Storage of finished/cooked food, (5) Transportation of food and (6) Serving food (Riyadi, 2023).

The practice of slaughtering animals in halal and *thayyibah* guarantees teaches the character values of faith and piety which are the main requirements for slaughterers; responsible, which is to be the guardian of halal guarantees to consumers; cooperate, because it cannot be done alone; like to share; and skilled.

(6) The commemoration of Islamic Holidays, involving the millennial generation in the committee.

The commemoration of Islamic Holidays is not only a routine activity but a transfer of knowledge and transfer of training, and is part of the process of internalizing Islamic values in building the character of the millennial generation. The commemoration of Islamic Holidays is usually filled with religious lectures and competitions, such as Qur'anic Recitation Competition with its various branches, and others of a religious nature. Religious lectures convey religious values either from historical, famous, or other scientific aspects. The points of religiosity values cover aspects of faith, worship, and morals, which are the basis for humans to carry out their activities (Hamdani et al., 2021).

The implementation of this program is by committee group work, which brings together people who have the characteristics of responsibility, discipline, hard work, cooperation, social care, and communicativeness. They work together to plan to carry out activities and evaluate them.

(7) Health and natural disaster mitigation

Based on the Law of the Republic of Indonesia No. 23 of 1992 concerning Health, it is declared healthy if a person, is physically, mentally, and spiritually able to do productive things in interaction with his environment both religiously, socially, and economically.

Mosques can be used as health centers and community care posts such as natural disaster mitigation, to serve economically disadvantaged people, who need assistance to recover from disasters that have befallen them. Sources of funds for the program can be raised from productive management of ZISWAF, grants, and CSR. The human resources involved in the implementation of the program are people who have the character of empathy and sympathy and can mobilize total,

selfless social care.

In general, the mosque plays a role in the formation of Islamic society; a medium for social interaction and acquaintance, and brotherhood (egalitarianism) of the community; knowledge development; pioneer of community economic development; scientific development; and even socio-cultural and political governance. The formation of Islamic society can only be done by righteous people, as Muhammad SAW did. When he first set foot in Cuba, the first thing he built was a mosque. Then the mosque became the center of Islamic community development in Medina. Similarly, the immigrants (Muslim traders who went to non-Muslim countries) built a mosque known as *zawiyah*, which had an attraction for non-Muslim people so that they embraced Islam, and an Islamic society was built around the *zawiyah*. Successively, the Muslim community living around the *zawiyah* migrated to other places, by establishing new *zawiyah*, until a new Islamic community was built again, until Islam reached Indonesia.

The mosque as a medium of *ta'aruf* and brotherhood (egalitarianism), guarantees people in a brotherhood based on humanity based on faith and piety, such as volunteer teams and fundraising in disaster mitigation. Mosques as institutions can develop science, even social culture, and politics, through the development of non-formal education programs such as Islamic learning assembly, socio-cultural and political studies, and so on. Science and mosque are one package. The mosque as a symbol of obedience and submission to Allah SWT is carried out based on science (Moslehi et al., 2023).

The mosque as a medium for developing the people's economy has implications for social life. The funds collected in the mosque are managed professionally and proportionally, with accountability and transparency. It should not be used up only for consumptive purposes. Because the entire mosque *takmir* activity program as an effort to optimize the role of the mosque requires costs that cannot be relied on by donors. Thus, the mosque should be a pioneer in the economic development of the people. The mosque can manage the mosque-based economy in various forms of halal business.

(8) *Ri'ayah* (matters relating to the physical building of the mosque, mosque facilities, and infrastructure, maintenance, cleanliness, and mosque security)

The mosque that has been built must get maintenance to maintain its splendor, beauty, purity, and cleanliness, so that every worshipper feels safe, comfortable, and calm when in the mosque. Including the environment around the mosque, which is green and cool because of the many plants, both trees and productive plants (Ma'zumi, 2019). The mosque *takmir* board is responsible for managing the mosque and working with members to plan for safety, beauty, and comfort. They also prepare facilities for worshipers, such as

libraries, education, and coaching programs. Overall, to build a community that qualifies as a prosperous mosque. Building an inclusive understanding of Islamic moderation is important, both in religious scholarship and religious experience. (Ma'zumi, 2019). Inclusiveness is important in addressing and appreciating differences of opinion and diversity in its various aspects. An inclusive attitude is indispensable in building harmony and peace both internally and between people.

The mosque facilities needed to serve the congregation are secretarial, lodging space for travelers, library space, adequate water, bathrooms and toilets, ablution places, security (such as CCTV), and wifi. To make the mosque setting comfortable and attractive, as well as to facilitate data search, the mosque yard can be built as a place to relax such as a canteen, coffee, or cafe. In addition, the mosque can become a learning medium for the millennial generation and increase the creativity and capacity of mosque managers to realize positive and productive internet utilization

CONCLUSION

The role of the mosque is very strategic in preparing a generation of *khairu ummah* (the best community). The generation that is the vision of its Creator. Through this generation, the role of the mosque as a civilization builder is expected to be achieved. Preparing a generation of *khairu ummah* requires a process that is not short, starting from the generation that will give birth to the generation, and is carried out continuously and continuously. Involving the millennial generation does not merely attract them to pray five times in congregation and be involved in empowering the mosque. No less important is to train proportional and professional skills in organization and responsible independence.

The implications of this study highlight the need for mosques to transform into adaptive and professionally managed institutions that integrate religious, educational, and socio-economic functions. Practically, mosque administrators (takmir) are encouraged to design structured, youth-oriented programs that align with the characteristics of millennials, including digital-based learning, leadership training, and community empowerment initiatives. Theoretically, this study contributes to the development of an integrative framework of mosque-based Islamic character education that bridges religious values with contemporary educational approaches. Furthermore, policymakers and Islamic educational institutions may utilize these findings to formulate strategies that strengthen the role of mosques as centers of character development and social transformation in modern society.

REFERENCES

- Ali, H. dan L. P. (2017). *Millennial Nusantara: Pahami Karakternya, Rebut Simpatinya*. Gramedia Pustaka Utama.
- Ali, M. Q., Al-Azhari, M. A. J., & Imran, M. (2020). An analysis of the teachings of muhammad (Saw) to conceptualize national professional standards for teachers: A contemporary issue. *Journal of Islamic Thought and Civilization*, 10(1), 349–363. <https://doi.org/10.32350/jitc.101.19>
- Alika Atha Amani, Saniyah Rizky Amalia, V. D. S. (2006). Eksplorasi Guru Pendidikan Agama Islam dalam Menanamkan Karakter Islami di SMP Muhammadiyah 4 Siurabaya. *Jurnal Pendidikan Dan Dakwah*, 3, 1421–1433.
- Amilda, Bujuri, D. A., Uyun, M., Nasrudin, D., & Junaidah. (2023). Patterns of Character Education for Vocational School Students through Non-Academic Programs: Paradigm and Implementation. *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*, 22(4), 459–477. <https://doi.org/10.26803/ijlter.22.4.25>
- Bakhmat, N., Kolosova, O., Demchenko, O., Ivashchenko, I., & Strelchuk, V. (2022). APPLICATION OF INTERNATIONAL SCIENTOMETRIC DATABASES IN THE PROCESS OF TRAINING COMPETITIVE RESEARCH AND TEACHING STAFF: OPPORTUNITIES OF WEB OF SCIENCE (WOS), SCOPUS, GOOGLE SCHOLAR. *Journal of Theoretical and Applied Information Technology*, 100(13), 4914–4924. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85134372365&partnerID=40&md5=2006f8eac72ba68d1e3a3713fdf0e993>
- Basuki, D. D., & Febriansyah, H. (2020). Pembentukan Karakter Islami melalui Pengembangan Mata Pelajaran Akidah Akhlak di Madrasah Aliyah An-Najah Bekasi. *Jurnal Pendidikan Dan Studi Keislaman*, 10(Agustus), 121–132.
- Bornstein, M. H., & Güngör, D. (2009). Organizing principles and processes from developmental science for culture and caregiving. In *Perspectives on Human Development, Family, and Culture* (pp. 69–85). <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511720437.008>
- Bulkani, B., Riadin, A., Ni'mah, N., & Setiawan, M. A. (2025). Impact of holistic learning models on character development: a systematic review. *Obrazovanie i Nauka*, 27(5), 111–141. <https://doi.org/10.17853/1994-5639-2025-5-111-141>
- Darmawan, D., & Marlin, S. (2021). Peran Masjid Bagi Generasi Milenial. *Jurnal Kajian Agama Hukum Dan Pendidikan Islam (KAHPI)*, 2(1), 52. <https://doi.org/10.32493/kahti.v2i1.p52-64.9372>
- Dewi, M. K. (2020). Pembentukan Karakter Islami Melalui Budaya Religius. *Akademika*, 2507(Desember), 123–132.
- Fitriani, R. N. (2021). *Konsep Pendidikan Karakter Islami*. Februari.
- Hakim, L. D. (2022). Implentasi Manajemen Masjid di Masjid Agung Darussalam Cilacap (

- Implementation of Mosque Management at the Great Mosque of Darussalam Cilacap). *Jurnal Ilmiah Stidki Ar-Rahmah*, 5(2), 25–31.
- Hamdani, D., Miftah, E., Ulwyah, R., & Utami, W. (2021). Pengaruh Peringatan Hari Besar Islam Terhadap Santri Al-Munawwir. *Proceedings UIN Sunan Gunung Djati Bandung, November*.
- Hidayat, A., Djafar, A. B., & Mawarny, E. (2023). Peran Masjid Kampus dalam Penguatan Moderasi Beragama (Studi Masjid Darul Ulum Universitas Pamulang). *Jurnal Kajian Agama Hukum Dan Pendidikan Islam (KAHPI)*, 4(2), 169–189.
- Jayanth, D. V, & Ganesha, K. S. (2025). Impact of Generational Culture of Gen Z and Millennials Towards Social Interaction and Community: Building in the Virtual World. In *Critical Ethical and Societal Implications of the Metaverse* (pp. 179–204). <https://doi.org/10.4018/979-8-3373-3043-3.ch007>
- Katsiroumpa, A., & Galanis, P. (2026). Thematic analysis in qualitative research. *Archives of Hellenic Medicine*, 43(3), 419–423. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-105033953317&partnerID=40&md5=c347742bf2cce9e72890b6648297224c>
- Ma'zumi. (2019). *Program Pemakmuran Masjid Kampus Dalam Pengembangan Kepribadian Islkami*. UIN SGD Bandung.
- Ma'zumi. (2022). Karakteristik Pemakmur Masjid Perspektif Syekh Nawawi Al-Bantany. *JAWARA-Jurnal Pendidikan Karakter*, 8(2), 1–19.
- Ma'zumi, Syihabudin, & Najmudin. (2023). The Effect of Islamic Character Education Factors on Green Entrepreneurial Behavior ; A Case of State University Students in Banten Province. *Edukasi Islami: Jurnal Pendidikan Islam*, 12(November), 2949–2962. <https://doi.org/10.30868/ei.v12i04.4410>
- Ma'zumi1, Saleh, S., & Maisaroh, I. (2023). Implikasi Dan Implementasi Pendidikan Karakter Di Era 4.0. *JAWARA-Jurnal Pendidikan Karakter*, 9(1), 25–41.
- Makarovič, M., & Rončević, B. (2020). Technology and Social Choices in the Era of Social Transformations. In *Technology and Social Choices in the Era of Social Transformations*. <https://doi.org/10.3726/b17652>
- Masyuhuri, A. A. (2018). *Kamus Super Lengkap Istilah-Istilah Agama Islam*. Diva Press.
- Moslehi, S., Dehghani, A., Masoumi, G., Sheikhi, R. A., & Barghi Shirazi, F. (2023). The Role of the Mosque as an Emergency Shelter in Disasters: A Systematic Review. *Health in Emergencies and Disasters Quarterly*, 8(Special Issue), 223–232. <https://doi.org/10.32598/hdq.8.specialissue.310.4>
- Mujahid, I. (2021). Islamic orthodoxy-based character education: creating moderate Muslim in a modern pesantren in Indonesia. *Indonesian Journal of Islam and Muslim Societies*, 11(2), 185–212. <https://doi.org/10.18326/ijims.v11i2.185-212>
- Osika, G. N. (2018). *Media Habit Generasi Milenial dalam Membaca Portal Berita NETZ*. Untirta Press.
- Ozuem, W., Willis, M., Howell, K., Lancaster, G., & Ng, R. (2021). Determinants of online brand

- communities' and millennials' characteristics: A social influence perspective. *Psychology and Marketing*, 38(5), 794–818. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mar.21470>
- Pradesyah, R., Susanti, D. A., & Rahman, A. (2021). Analisis Manajemen Keuangan Masjid Dalam Pengembangan Dana Masjid. *Misykat Al-Anwar Jurnal Kajian Islam Dan Masyarakat*, 4(2), 153. <https://doi.org/10.24853/ma.4.2.153-170>
- Riyadi, F. (2023). Peran dan Kompetensi Juru Sembelih Halal (JULEHA) Perspektif Hukum Islam. *TAWAZUN: Journal of Sharia Economic Law*, 6(1), 157. <https://doi.org/10.21043/tawazun.v6i1.21254>
- Sarwono, J. (2006). *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif dan Kualitatif*. Graha Ilmu.
- Statistik, B. P. (2018). *Statistik Gender Tematik: Profil Generasi Milenial Indonesia*. Kementerian Pemberdayaan Perempuan dan Perlindungan Anak.
- Taufik, M. (2020). Strategic Role of Islamic Religious Education in Strengthening Character Education in the Era of Industrial Revolution 4.0. *Jurnal Ilmiah Islam Futura*, 20(1), 86–104. <https://doi.org/10.22373/jiif.v20i1.5797>
- Wibowo, H. S., Muiz, A. H., & Yudoyono, N. N. (2023). Strategi Marketing Program Kajian Pada Masjid Anak Muda (Marketing Strategy Of Study Program On Youth Mosques). *Jurnal Ilmiah Stidki Ar-Rahmah*, 5(2022), 19–24.
- Yoris Sebastian, Dilla Amran, Y. (2016). *Generasi langgas : millennials Indonesia*. Gagas Media.
- Yuliharti, Y. (2019). Pembentukan Karakter Islami Dalam Hadis Dan Implikasinya Pada Jalur Pendidikan Non Formal. *POTENSIA: Jurnal Kependidikan Islam*, 4(2), 216. <https://doi.org/10.24014/potensia.v4i2.5918>
- Zaim, M. (2020). Media Pembelajaran Agama Islam Di Era Milenial 4.0. *Jurnal Kependidikan Islam*, 6(1), 1–17.